

C-IMMSIM simulation results

August 16, 2025

Abstract

This document includes the plots relative to the simulation and the outcome of the epitope/peptide prediction used.

Produced by the C-IMMSIM Online server available at
<http://c-immsim.iac.rm.cnr.it> (alias to <http://kraken.iac.rm.cnr.it/C-IMMSIM>)

CITATIONS: For publication of results, please cite the following:

Nicolas Rapin, Ole Lund, Massimo Bernaschi, Filippo Castiglione. Computational Immunology Meets Bioinformatics: The Use of Prediction Tools for Molecular Binding in the Simulation of the Immune System. PLoS ONE 5(4): e9862
doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0009862, 2010

A retrospective validation

In-silico evaluation of adenoviral COVID-19 vaccination protocols: Assessment of immunological memory up to 6 months after the third dose. P. Stolfi, F. Castiglione, E. Mastrostefano, I. Di Biase, S. Di Biase, G. Palmieri, A. Prisco. Frontiers in Immunology, 13 (2022) doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262>

An in vivo validation

Identification and validation of viral antigens sharing sequence and structural homology with tumor associated antigens (TAAs). C. Ragone, C. Manolio, B. Cavalluzzo, A. Petrizzo, A. Mauriello, M-L. Tornesello, F. M. Buonaguro, F. Castiglione, L. Vitagliano, M. Ruvo, M. Tagliamonte, L. Buonaguro. Journal for ImmunoTherapy of Cancer. 9:e002694 (2021)
<https://jitc.bmj.com/content/9/5/e002694>

Original C-IMMSIM model: www.iac.cnr.it/~filippo/c-immsim

GETTING HELP:

Scientific problems: Filippo Castiglione (filippo dot castiglione at cnr dot it)

Technical problems: Ilaria Gonnella (ilaria dot gonnella at cnr dot it)

Figure 1: Cell counts shown. Legend: Act=active, Intern=internalized the Ag, Pres II = presenting on MHC II, Dup = in the mitotic cycle, Anergic = anergic, Resting = not active.

Figure 2: Legend: symbols as figure above.

Figure 3: The virus, the immunoglobulins and the immunocomplexes.

Figure 4: Concentration of cytokines and interleukins. Inset plot shows danger signal together with leukocyte growth factor IL-2.

0] pos= 146 score=0.007794 unnormalised=0.8236000000 TTVESHGNY
1] pos= -1 score=0.992206 unnormalised=104.8410000000 non-binding event

=====
Allele: A0101
Pseudo sequence: KAVHAEQRNKAQTRA
Threshold: 9.456400
Max score: 29.236000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250816-142647_5_tBwTzn2NG8L.FSA_1_001

FNCLGMSNRDFLEGVSGATWVDLVLEGDSVCTIMSKDKPTIDVKMMNMEANLAEVRSYCYLATVSELSTKAACPTMGEA
HNDKRADPSFVCKQGVVDRGWNGCGLFGKGSIDTCAKFACSTKATGRTILKENIKYEVAIFVHGPTTVESHGNYFTQTG
AAQAGRFSITPAAPSYTLKLGEGYEVTVDCPRSGIDTSAYYVMTVGTKTFLVHREWFMDLNLWPSSAESNVWRNREITLM
EFEEPHATKQSVIALGSEQEGALHQAALAGAIPEVSSNTVKLTSGHLKCRVKMEKLQLKGTTYGVCSKAFRFLGTPADTGH
GTVVLELQYTGTDGPKIPISSVASLNDLTPVGRLVTNPFVSVSTANAKVLIELEPPFGDSYIVVGRGEQQINHHWHKS
G

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0] pos= 146 score=0.007794 unnormalised=0.8236000000 TTVESHGNY
1] pos= -1 score=0.992206 unnormalised=104.8410000000 non-binding event

=====
Allele: B0702
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQIKAQTRE
Threshold: 8.702800
Max score: 28.406000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250816-142647_5_tBwTzn2NG8L.FSA_1_001

FNCLGMSNRDFLEGVSGATWVDLVLEGDSVCTIMSKDKPTIDVKMMNMEANLAEVRSYCYLATVSELSTKAACPTMGEA
HNDKRADPSFVCKQGVVDRGWNGCGLFGKGSIDTCAKFACSTKATGRTILKENIKYEVAIFVHGPTTVESHGNYFTQTG
AAQAGRFSITPAAPSYTLKLGEGYEVTVDCPRSGIDTSAYYVMTVGTKTFLVHREWFMDLNLWPSSAESNVWRNREITLM
EFEEPHATKQSVIALGSEQEGALHQAALAGAIPEVSSNTVKLTSGHLKCRVKMEKLQLKGTTYGVCSKAFRFLGTPADTGH
GTVVLELQYTGTDGPKIPISSVASLNDLTPVGRLVTNPFVSVSTANAKVLIELEPPFGDSYIVVGRGEQQINHHWHKS
G

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0] pos= 169 score=0.064675 unnormalised=7.8712000000 TPAAPSYTL
1] pos= 243 score=0.013173 unnormalised=1.6032000000 EPHATKQSV
2] pos= 337 score=0.044618 unnormalised=5.4302000000 IPISSVASL
3] pos= 349 score=0.005408 unnormalised=0.6582000000 TPVGRLVTV
4] pos= 358 score=0.010683 unnormalised=1.3002000000 NPFVSVSTA
5] pos= -1 score=0.861443 unnormalised=104.8410000000 non-binding event

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FNCLGMSNRDFLEGVSGATWVDLVLEGDSCVTIMSKDKPTIDVKMMNMEANLAEVRSYCYLATVSELSTKAACPTMGEA
HNDKRADPSFVCKQGVVDRGWNGCGLFGKGSIDTCAKFACSTKATGRITLKENIKYEVAIFVHGPTTVESHGNYFTQTG
AAQAGRFSITPAAPSYTLKLGEGYEVTVDCPRSGIDTSAYYVMTVGTKTFLVHREWFMDLNLWPSSAESNVWRNRETL
EFEEPHATKQSVIALGSEQEGALHLAGAIPVEFSSNTVKLTSGHLKCRVKMEKQLKLGTTYGVCSKAFRLGTPADTGH
GTVVLELQYTGTDGPKIPISSVASLNDLTPVGRLVTVPFVSVSTANAKVLIIELEPPFGDSYIVVGRGEQQINHHWHKS
G

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 169	score=0.064675	unnormalised=7.8712000000	TPAAPSYTL
1]	pos= 243	score=0.013173	unnormalised=1.6032000000	EPHATKQSV
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4]	pos= 358	score=0.010683	unnormalised=1.3002000000	NPFVSVSTA
5]	pos= -1	score=0.861443	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

DoPeptideList_II:

Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the
NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 2 MHCII molecules

Read class II peptide list from file? NO

=====
Allele: DRB1_0101
Pseudo sequence: KFAHVEQRKAQTRV
Threshold: 2.392440
Max score: 26.461000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250816-142647_5_tBwBtzn2NG8L.FSA_1_001

FNCLGMSNRDFLEGVSGATWVDLVLEGDSCVTIMSKDKPTIDVKMMNMEANLAEVRSYCYLATVSELSTKAACPTMGEA
HNDKRADPSFVCKQGVVDRGWNGCGLFGKGSIDTCAKFACSTKATGRITLKENIKYEVAIFVHGPTTVESHGNYFTQTG
AAQAGRFSITPAAPSYTLKLGEGYEVTVDCPRSGIDTSAYYVMTVGTKTFLVHREWFMDLNLWPSSAESNVWRNRETL
EFEEPHATKQSVIALGSEQEGALHLAGAIPVEFSSNTVKLTSGHLKCRVKMEKQLKLGTTYGVCSKAFRLGTPADTGH
GTVVLELQYTGTDGPKIPISSVASLNDLTPVGRLVTVPFVSVSTANAKVLIIELEPPFGDSYIVVGRGEQQINHHWHKS
G

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 10	score=0.002542	unnormalised=0.4075600000	FLEGVSGAT
1]	pos= 42	score=0.016042	unnormalised=2.5715600000	VKMMNMEAA
2]	pos= 44	score=0.053328	unnormalised=8.5485600000	MMNMEANL
3]	pos= 45	score=0.057720	unnormalised=9.2525600000	MNMEANLA
4]	pos= 58	score=0.014701	unnormalised=2.3565600000	YCYLATVSE
5]	pos= 60	score=0.053834	unnormalised=8.6295600000	YLATVSELS
6]	pos= 134	score=0.014408	unnormalised=2.3095600000	IKYEVAIFV
7]	pos= 154	score=0.028618	unnormalised=4.5875600000	YFTQTGAAQ
8]	pos= 155	score=0.063035	unnormalised=10.1045600000	FTQTGAAQA
9]	pos= 166	score=0.064570	unnormalised=10.3505600000	FSITPAAPS
10]	pos= 168	score=0.035131	unnormalised=5.6315600000	ITPAAPSYT
11]	pos= 201	score=0.042025	unnormalised=6.7365600000	YVMTVGTKT
12]	pos= 218	score=0.004545	unnormalised=0.7285600000	MDLNLWPSS
13]	pos= 239	score=0.008980	unnormalised=1.4395600000	MEFEEPHAT
14]	pos= 251	score=0.009854	unnormalised=1.5795600000	VIALGSEQE
15]	pos= 261	score=0.042842	unnormalised=6.8675600000	LHQUALAGAI
16]	pos= 273	score=0.001844	unnormalised=0.2955600000	FSSNTVKLT
17]	pos= 308	score=0.002898	unnormalised=0.4645600000	FRFLGTPAD
18]	pos= 310	score=0.016959	unnormalised=2.7185600000	FLGTPADTG

19]	pos= 354	score=0.007702	unnormalised=1.2345600000	LVTVNPVFS
20]	pos= 360	score=0.045649	unnormalised=7.3175600000	FVSVSTANA
21]	pos= -1	score=0.412774	unnormalised=66.1680000000	non-binding event

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Allele: DRB1_0101
Pseudo sequence: KAFHVEQRKAQTRV
Threshold: 2.392440
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FNCLGMSNRDFLEGVSGATWVDLVLEGDSVCTIMSKDKPTIDVKMMNMEANLAEVRSYCYLATVSELSTKAACPTMGEA
HNDKRADPSFVCKQGVVDRGWGNGCFLGKGSIDTCAKFACTKATGRTILKENIKYEVAIFVHGPTTVESHGNYFTQTG
AAQAGRFSITPAAPSYTLKLEGEYEVTVDCPEPRSGIDTSAYYVMTVGTKTFLVHREWFMDLNLPWSSAESNVWRNREITLM
EFEEPHATKQSVIALGSEQEGALHQAAGAIPEVSSNTVKLTSGHLKCRVKMEKQLKGTTYGVCSKAFRFLGTPADTGH
GTVVLELQYTGTDGPKIPISSVASLNDLTPVGRVTVNPVFSVSTANAKVLIELEPPFGDSYIVVGRGEQQINHHWHKS
G

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

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1]	pos= 42	score=0.016042	unnormalised=2.5715600000	VKMMNMEAA
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6]	pos= 134	score=0.014408	unnormalised=2.3095600000	IKYEVAIFV
7]	pos= 154	score=0.028618	unnormalised=4.5875600000	YFTQTGAAQ
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21]	pos= -1	score=0.412774	unnormalised=66.1680000000	non-binding event